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Socio-Economic Characteristics and Constraints Associated With the Adoption of the Improved Shea Nut Processing Technologies in Niger State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The objectives of this paper were to assess the socio-economic characteristics and constraints associated with the adoption of the improved Shea nut processing technologies in Niger State, Nigeria. The result of socio-economic characteristics of the Shea nut processors shows that majority (60.00%) were between the age range of 41 – 50 years and the average of age Shea nut processors in the study area was 42.07. The result also revealed that all (100%) of the processors were female processors. The result revealed that all (100%) of the processors adopted the use of bare hand. The result indicated that all (100.00%) of the processors used room /stores floors for the storage of Shea butter. The result revealed that membership of cooperative (X_9) marital status (X_5) and extension contact (X_8) were significant at 1% level of significance and had positive relationship with the level of adoption of improved Shea nut processing technologies. The result also revealed that age, processing experience and membership of association were related to adoption and statistically significant at 5% level of probability among the selected socio-economic characteristics. The result also show that age (X_1) was negatively significant at 0.05% probability levels with adoption of improved Shea nut processing technologies. It is recommended that organized big term marketers in the Shea industry should form, organize more associations and trainings of pickers/collectors, processors and marketers' of Shea nut at the grass roots for optimal utilization of its value chains and income generation.

Keywords: Shea nut, Socio economic, Technologies, Processing, Adoption.

INTRODUCTION

Shea tree (*Vitellaria paradoxa*) grows in a large part of sub-Saharan Africa. The tree is important for the livelihood of rural population for centuries. Almost every part of Shea trees is useful for example, the fruit is eaten and the leaves are used as fodder for livestock and serve as an ingredient for making alkaline and paint for industrial purposes (Lovett and Haq, 2000).

The butter that is either traditionally or mechanically extracted from Shea nut which are produced by Shea trees also have a lot of end-use applications which include: valuable oil for cooking, cosmetics and skincare, pharmaceutical and medicinal uses. The oil extracted from the seeds may have up to 50% oil content and when refined, Shea oil is used as a substitute for margarine and cocoa butter in the food industries (Suleiman, 2008).

Shea butter has great economic and nutritional potentials both locally and internationally and the demand for the commodity experiencing a steady increase yearly (Suleiman, 2008). Shea nut products command an important position in the diet of the rural people in Northern Nigeria, children, women and men eat the fruit while it is raw and the processed crude oil is also used as a food component. In most Northern villages, where cooking oil is scarce, Shea oil serves as a close substitute that is used for cooking all traditional foods (Lovett and Haq, 2000; Suleiman, 2008). Apart from the nutritional potentials of Shea butter, it generates income specifically for women as it is traditionally seen as women's business. Shea oil provides a major source of income to households engaged in its trade and has a higher gain when compared to other crops such as groundnut and maize (Elias and Carney, 2007; Lovett and Haq, 2000).

Presently Shea nut and butter are exported from Africa countries to France, Great Britain, the Nether land, Denmark, North America, and Japan (Elias & Carney, 2007). In these countries, it is processed in a wide range of food products including chocolate and it is becoming more popular in the cosmetic industry (Schreckerberg, 2000). Niger state ranked top among the Sheanuts producing states in Nigeria which include Kwara, Nasarrawa, Zamfara,

Kaduna, Sokoto, Jigawa, Kano, Plateau, Taraba, Benue, Adamawa, Bauchi, Kebbi, Edo, Yobe and Federal Capital Territory (FCT), Abuja. Based on recent events, the interest on the Shea nut oil (Shea butter) produced from Shea nut for industrial application in food, cosmetics, pharmaceutical and traditional needs at national and international levels has increased (Suleiman, 2008).

Shea nut handling and marketing are the most challenging stages in the value chain process. There are lack of standard and quality control in the way and manner Shea nut are locally handled. The parboiling, drying, packaging and storage stages require modernization and control if high quality Shea butter/oil are to be obtained. The prices offered for Shea nut in wet and dry seasons tend to vary considerably and are usually determined by the middlemen. The established price for one tone of Shea butter varies from one season to another pending on the availability of the Shea nut during the season. Unfortunately, Shea nut production and export fall far below demand. Thus calling for an intervention to increase the supply and also improve the quality of Shea butter for domestic and commercial purposes.

The objective of the study was to assess the socio-economic characteristics and constraints associated with the adoption of improved Shea nut processing technologies as well as identifying the various methods of improved Shea nut processing technologies.

METHODOLOGY

Area of study

The study was carried out in Niger state where there is a lot of wild Shea tree plantation for domestic and commercial purposes. The state falls in the guinea savannah zone and has a climate and ecological conditions that favors agricultural production. It has an annual rainfall of between 1100mm – 1600mm and has an average temperature of 35°C (Gbako, 1991). The state has abundant wild vegetation of Shea trees and is dominated by small-scale farmers. The major crops cultivated in the State are millet, rice, maize, guinea corn, beans, cassava, groundnuts and sweet potatoes. Majority of the farmers keep livestock like poultry, goats and sheep. Others engage in crafts such as sculptures, weaving and blacksmith (Publication of Projects and Programmes Documentation Unit, PPDU, (2009). Based on the 2006 National Population Census, the state has a total projected human population of 4,250,429 as at 2006.

Materials and Methods

The multi-stage procedure was used for the research. The first stage was the purposive selection of the state for the study because of the abundance of wild vegetation of Shea trees in the state. The second stage also involves purposive selection of Zone I based on the predominance of Shea trees (Suleiman, 2008). Simple random sampling technique was then applied to select three (3) Local Government Areas in the zone, namely: Gbako, Katcha and Agaie. The third stage was the random selection of six (6) extension cells from each extension block making a total of eighteen (18) extension cells. From the cells a total of thirty one (31) registered Shea nut processing villages were purposively selected based on the frequency of Shea nut processing activities. Finally, from the existing list of 412 Shea nut processors with the state ADP, presently known and called Niger State Agricultural Mechanization and Development Agency (NAMDA), the state of Ministry Cooperatives, the Ministry of Women Affairs and GIZ State Field Office in Minna, 37 percent of the processors were randomly selected. This percent of the total population was taken giving to obtain total sample size of 150 Shea nut processors as shown in Table 1. The sample size was selected at 5% precision level and at confidence level of 95% (Isreal, 1992).

Table 1: Distribution of sampled Shea nut processors

Extension Block	Extension Cells	Number of Registered Shea nut Processors	Number of Villages Selected	Numbers of Processors Selected
Gbako	6	118	9	43
Katcha	6	143	10	52
Agaie	6	151	12	55
Total	18	412	31	150

Data Collection and Instrument for data

The data for the study were mainly obtained from primary source. Primary data was collected from a cross-sectional survey of registered Shea nut processors through the use of an interview schedule with the assistance of trained enumerators that can communicate freely with the native language of the people in the study area.

Analytical Techniques

Descriptive statistics which include measure of central tendency, such as percentages, means and measures of variation such as variance and standard deviation were used to achieve the objectives of the study.

Specification of Model

In testing the hypotheses, the following statistical tools were employed:

Binomial logistic regression model was used to test for significant relationship between socio-economic characteristics and processors' level of adoption of improved Shea nut processing technologies in the study area. The model was used to determine the factors that influence the adoption of improved Shea nut processing technologies. The independent variable (adoption level) was categorized into two levels on the basis of the number of technologies adopted by the processors. The processors that adopted 1 to ≤ 8 of the technologies are classified as low adopters and scored 0 while processors that adopted 9 to ≥ 17 technologies are classified as high adopters and scored 1.

The binomial logistic regression model for determination of significant relationship between adoption level of Shea nut processors and the processors socio-economic characteristics is expressed as:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \beta_5 X_5 + \dots + \beta_n X_n \quad \dots (1)$$

Where

$Y = 1$ if the adoption level of the specified improved Shea nut processing technology is high, 0 if the adoption level is low

Age (X_1)

Sex (X_2)

Education (X_3)

Household size (X_4)

Marital status (X_5)

Processing experience (X_6)

Training (X_7)

Extension contact (X_8)

Cooperative membership (X_9)

Income (X_{10})

Quantity (X_{11})

All these variables represent the vector of explanatory (independent) variables and β , are the coefficient of parameters to be estimated.

Pearson correlation coefficient was used to test the hypotheses while hypotheses three to five was tested using Pearson product moment correlation (PPMC).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 2: Distribution of the Shea nut processors according to socio-economic characteristics (n=150)

Socio-economic characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
31 – 40	55	36.67
41 – 50	90	60.00
51-60	5	3.33
Gender		
Female	150	100.00
Marital Status		
Married	117	78.00
Single	33	22.00
Education		
Primary	14	9.33
Secondary	8	5.55
Adult	128	85.33
Household Size		
1-5	5	3.33
6-10	61	40.67
11-15	64	42.67
Above 15	20	13.33
Processing experience		
Less than 10	2	1.34
10-20	62	41.34
Above 20	86	57.34
Extension contact		
Yes	129	86.00
No	21	24.00
Processing centre		
Yes	93	62.00
No	57	38.00
Membership of association		
Yes	123	82.00
No	27	18.00

Source: Field survey, 2012

Table 2 shows the percentage distributions of the Shea nut processors by age. The results revealed that majority (60.00%) of the processors fall within the age range of 41 – 50 years while 36.6% were 31-40 years old. The mean ages of the processors were 42.07 years.

Table 2 shows the percentage distribution of the Shea nut processors by gender. The results revealed that all (100%) of the processors were female. This implies that Shea nut processing is mainly undertaken by women

Table 2 shows the percentage distribution of Shea nut processors by marital status. The results shows that majority (78.00%) of the Shea nut processors were married. This implies that majority of the Shea nut processors in the study area have additional responsibilities of catering for their households.

Table 2 shows the percentage distribution of Shea nut processors by level of education. The results revealed that most of the processors had only attended adult literacy classes. This implies that processors had very low level of education.

Table 2 shows the percentage distribution of Shea nut processors by household size. The results indicated that (42.67%) of the Shea nut processors had household size ranging from 11 – 15 people. Only few (3.33%) of the processors had a household size of 1-5 people. This implies that majority of the Shea nut processors had large family sizes, which will provide family labour for processing. The mean household size of Shea nut processors in the study area was 11.34 persons.

Table 2 shows the percentage distribution of the Shea nut processors by processing experience. The results indicated that majority (57.34%) of the processors had more than 20 years of processing experience, and only 1.34% of the processors had less than 10 years of processing experience. This implies that the Shea nut processors in the study area had acquired enough processing experience that will encourage them to adopt improved Shea nut processing technologies.

Table .2 shows the percentage distribution of the Shea nut processors by processing centre. The results revealed that majority (63.00%) of the processors had processing centres. This implies that the Shea nut processors had avenues to interact and share ideas about improved Shea nut processing technologies which can facilitate the adoption of the technologies.

Tables 2 revealed that majority (82.00%) of the processors were members of one cooperative or the other. This implies that the members stand a better chance of receiving assistance from government and non-governmental organizations (NGOs) or donor agencies.

Table 3: Distribution of the Shea nut processors according to number of training received (n=150)

Number of training received	Frequency	Percentage
0	61	40.67
1	84	56.00
2	5	3.33

Source: Field survey, 2012

Table 3 shows the percentage distribution of the Shea nut processors by training received. The results indicated that majority (56.00%) of the Shea nut processors had received training once, while 40.67% of the processors had no training. Only (3.33%) of the processors received the training twice. This implies that majority of the Shea nut processors had need for more training.

Table 4: Distribution of the Shea nut processors according to Sources of credit and labour (n=150)

Source of credit	Frequency	Percentage
Personal	44	29.33
Family	58	38.66
Friends and neighbors	48	32.00
Labour		
Family	121	80.66
Communal	27	18.00
Hired	1	0.66
Friends and neighbours	1	0.66

Source: Field survey, 2012

Table 4 reveals that 38.66% of the processors used personal savings while 32.60% and 29.33% of the processors obtained their credits from family and cooperative associations respectively. This implies that the processors did not patronize formal sources of credit such as commercial banks.

The results in Table 4 revealed that majority (80.66%) of the processors used family labour to process Shea nut while 18.00% used communal labour. Only 0.66% of the processors used hired labour. This implies that majority of the processors do not incurred extra expenses on labour.

Methods of Shea nut processing technologies adopted

Picking of mature dropped fruits

Table 5 shows the percentage distribution of the Shea nut processors for picking of mature dropped fruits. The results revealed that all (100%) of the processors adopted the use of bare hand. This implies that the Shea nuts gatherers depend mainly on the traditional methods of Shea nut picking.

Condition of collection of mature dropped Shea fruits

Table 5 shows the percentage distribution of the Shea nut processors for stages of collection of dropped Shea fruits. The results revealed that majority (70.00%) of the processors adopted the picking of only ripped fruits of Shea nut, while few (30.00%) of the processors adopted the picking of over-ripped fruits of Shea nut. This implies that the Shea nut processors were aware of the important stages of Shea nut collection which directly or indirectly affect Shea butter quality.

Materials used in collection of Shea nut

Table 5 shows the percentage distribution of the Shea nut processors for materials used in collection of Shea nut. The results revealed that majority (97.33%) of the processors adopted head pans as one of the materials used for the collection of Shea nut. While very few (2.00%) of the processors adopted the use of buckets and (0.67%) of the processor adopted the use of jute bags as materials for collection of Shea nut from the wild Shea plantations. Processors being women were already used to the use of head pan as a material for the collection of nuts from the wild Shea plantation.

De-pulping of Shea nut

Table 5 shows the percentage distribution of the Shea nut processors for de-pulping of Shea nut. The results revealed that about 38.67% of the processors directly removed and discard mesocarp for de-pulping of Shea nut, 38.00% of the processors adopted the use of hot water for de-pulping of Shea nut. And 22.33% of the processors consumed the mesocarp for de-pulping of Shea nut. This implies that the Shea nut processors used different methods of de-pulping Shea nut for processing.

Drying of Shea nut

Table 5 shows the percentage distribution of the Shea nut processors for drying of Shea nut. The results revealed that majority (64.67%) of the processors adopted the use of sun drying of Shea nut and about 33.33% use local oven drying method. This implies that the Shea nut processors had access to only two methods of drying of Shea nut.

Parboiling of Shea nut

Table 5 shows the percentage distribution of the processors for Parboiling of Shea nut. The results revealed that majority (58.00%) of the Shea nut processors adopted the use of aluminum pots/firewood as materials for the parboiling of Shea nut while 42.00% of the processors adopted the use of drum/ firewood as materials for the parboiling of Shea nut. This implies that the Shea nut processors were used to the traditional materials for the parboiling of Shea nut for Shea nut processing.

De-husking of Shea nut

Table 5 shows the percentage distribution of the Shea nut processors for de-husking of Shea nut. The results revealed that 47.33% of the processors adopted the use of mortar and piston as materials for de-husking of Shea nut and 26.67% of the processors used stone as a material for the de-husking of Shea nut, while, 26.00% of the processors used stick for the de-husking of Shea nut. This implies that the Shea nut processors were already aware of the important of de-husking as a technology for the processing of Shea butter.

Sorting/grading of Shea nut

Table 5 shows the percentage distribution of the Shea nut processors for sorting /grading of Shea nut. The results revealed that majority (60.00%) of processors adopted the collection of un-damaged Shea nut for the processing, while 38.67% of the processors used damaged fruits for processing. This implies that the Shea nut processors used both damaged and undamaged fruits for processing.

Roasting of Shea nut

Table 5 shows the percentage distribution of the processors for roasting of Shea nut. The results revealed that all (100.00%) of the processors used frying pans with firewood as materials for the roasting of Shea nut for processing.

This implies that the Shea nut processors had knowledge of the important of roasting of Shea nut as a technology for achieving better quality Shea butter.

Pounding/crushing of Shea nut

Table 5 shows the percentage distribution of the Shea nut processors for pounding/crushing of Shea nut. The results revealed that majority (74.67%) of the processors adopted the use of mortar and piston as instruments for pounding/crushing of Shea nut, while, few 25.33% of processors used machine for crushing of Shea nut. This implies that only few processors had access to modern technology of using machine for crushing of Shea nut.

Grinding of Shea nut

Table 5 shows the percentage distribution of the Shea nut processors for grinding of Shea nut paste. The results revealed that all (100.00%) of the processors used of mechanical machine (grinding machine) for the grinding of Shea nut into paste. This implies that the Shea nut processors had knowledge of the effectiveness and efficiency in the use of mechanical machine for processing of quality Shea butter.

Kneading/churning/mixing of Shea nut paste

Table 5 shows the percentage distribution of the Shea nut processors for kneading/churning/mixing of Shea nut paste. The result revealed that 33.33% of the processors used cold water kneading with mortar and hand in Shea butter kneading, while 44.00% of the processors used warm water kneading with mortar and hand for kneading of Shea nut paste. This implies that the processors used both kneading methods in achieving good quality Shea butter.

Boiling of kneaded Shea nut paste

Table 5 shows the percentage distribution of the Shea nut processors for boiling of kneaded Shea nut paste. The results revealed that all (100.00%) of the processors boiling used local pots and firewood as materials for boiling of kneaded Shea nut paste. This implies that the processors had access to only local materials for the boiling of kneaded Shea nut paste.

Adding of deodorant during boiling

Table 5 shows the percentage distribution of the Shea nut processors for adding of deodorant during boiling. The results revealed that majority (68.00%) of the processors adopted the use of potassium as deodorant during boiling. This implies that the processors had knowledge of how to process odour-less Shea butter that will attract better market price.

Clarification/separation of Shea butter from water and impurities

Table 5 shows the percentage distribution of the Shea nut processors for clarification/separation of Shea butter from water/impurities. The results revealed that majority (64.00%) of the processors adopted the use of clean cloth for clarification/separation of Shea butter from water/impurities. While 36.00% of the processors used long spoon for sieving of Shea butter from water/impurities in Shea butter. This implies that the processors know the importance of removing water and impurities from Shea butter to enable, obtain premium quality Shea butter.

Packaging of Shea butter

Table 5 shows the percentage distribution of the Shea nut processors for packaging of Shea butter. The results revealed that half (50.00%) of the processors used plastic containers for packaging of Shea butter. 42.00% of the processors used iron container for packaging of Shea butter and only 8.00% of the processor used leather/cartons for the packaging of Shea butter. This implies that the processors had knowledge of different packaging methods for preservation that will attract better market price.

Storage of Shea butter

Table 5 shows the percentage distribution of the Shea nut processors by storage of Shea butter. The results revealed that all (100.00%) of the processors used room /stores floors for the storage of Shea butter. This implies

that the processors only had access to room/ store floors for the storage of Shea butter, and that the processors do not have special facilities for the storage of Shea butter.

Table 5: Distribution of processors according to methods of improved Shea nut processing technologies adopted (n=150)

Methods of improved Shea nut production	Frequency	Percentage
Picking of mature dropped fruits/nut		
Bare hand	150	100.00
Condition of collection of mature dropped fruits/nut		
Ripe only	105	70.00
Both ripe and over ripe	45	30.00
Materials use in collection of Shea nut		
Head pans	146	97.33
Buckets	3	2.00
Jute bags	1	0.67
De-pulping of Shea nut		
Eat mesocarp	35	23.33
Remove and discard	35	38.67
Use of hot water	57	38.00
Drying of Shea nut		
Sun drying	97	64.67
Local oven drying	53	35.33
Parboiling of Shea nut		
Use aluminum pots/firewood	87	58.00
Use of drum/firewood	63	42.00
De-husking of Shea nut		
Use of stone	40	26.67
Mortar and piston	71	47.33
Use of stick	39	26.00
Sorting/Grading of Shea nut		
Damaged Shea nut	58	38.67
Undamaged Shea nut	92	61.33
Roasting of Shea Nut		
Use of frying pan with firewood	150	100.00
Pounding/crushing of Shea nut		
Use of mortar and piston	112	74.67
Use of machine	38	25.33
Grinding of Shea nut Paste		
Use of mechanical machines (grinding machine)	150	100.00
Kneading/churning/mixing/washing of paste of Shea nut		
Warm water kneading/mortar/hand	81	44.67
Cold water kneading/mortar/hand	69	55.33
Boiling of kneaded Shea nut paste		
Use of local pots and firewood and long local spoon	150	100.00
Adding of deodorant to Shea butter during boiling		
Onions	45	30.00
Use of salt	3	2.00
Potassium	102	68.00
Clarification/separation of Shea butter from water		
Use of clean cloth	96	64.00
Sieving with long spoon	54	36.00
Packaging of Shea butter		
Iron containers	63	42.00
Plastic containers	75	50.00
Leathers/cartons	12	8.00
Storage of Shea butter		
Room/floor	150	100.00

Source: Field survey, 2012

Relationship between socio-economic characteristics and processors level of adoption of improved Shea nut processing technologies

The hypothesis was tested using binomial logistic regression analysis at 0.05% probability level. The results revealed that membership of cooperative (X_9), marital status (X_5) and extension contact (X_8) were significant at 1% level of significance and had positive relationship with the level of adoption of improved Shea nut processing technologies. This implies that apart from easiness of access to production resources, processors that were members of cooperative organizations interact and share ideas on the advantages associated with adoption of improved Shea nut processing technologies. Similarly, marital status is a proxy of source of large household size which can serve as source of labour for the processors. Hence, Shea nut processors that are married are most likely to have more helping hands in the processing of Shea butter.

The results also show that age (X_1) was negatively significant at 0.05% probability levels with adoption of improved Shea nut processing technologies. This implies that as the processors grows older the tendency to accept and adopt new processing technologies decreases.

Table 6: Binomial logistic regression result of adoption level and some socio-economic characteristics

Adoption level	Coefficients	Standard error	Z values	P> Z
Age	-.0669801**	.0367528	-1.82	0.068
Household size	-.106529	.1474022	-0.72	0.470 NS
Educational level	.0949456	.0699154	1.36	0.174 NS
Cooperative mem.	2.26534***	.6837582	3.31	0.001
Marital status	2.26534	.6837582	3.31	0.001
Processing exp.	.0315767***	.05135 4	0.61	0.539
Ext. contact	2.43678***	.4206358	5.79	0.000
Quantity proc.	.0009725**	.0005503	-1.77	0.077
Constraints	-3.247832**	1.954347	-1.66	0.097

Source; Field survey, 2012

N.B * = Significant at 0.10% level ** = Significant at 0.05% level, ***Significant at 0.01%,NS=Non Significant

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Shea nut processing activities is mainly women business, majority of the processors had processing centres and also belongs to different Shea butter processing associations. The study also revealed that majority were trained either by government or non-governmental organizations (NGOs)/donor agencies on the improved Shea nut processing technologies.

The study also indicated that age, processing experience and membership of association were related to adoption and statistically significant at 5% level of probability among the selected socio- economic characteristics. It is recommended that organized big term marketers in the Shea industry should form, organize more associations and trainings of pickers/collectors, processors and marketers' of Shea nut at the grass roots for optimal utilization of its value chains and income generation.

REFERENCES

- Elias, M. & Carney, J. (2007). Africa Shea butter; A feminized subsidy from nature, *Africa* 77(1) Pp.34-53.
- Gbako, (1991). Focus on Gbako Local Government, Lemu, Niger State. Information pamphlet. Pp.1-5.
- Lovett & Haq, (2000). Evidence for Anthropique Selection of the Shea nut Tree (*Vitellaria Paradoxa*). *Agro-forestry Systems Journal*, 48: 73 – 88.
- Publication of Projects and Programmes Documentation Unit ,PPDU,(2009) Office of the Governor No. 1, Shehu A. Musa Road by Aliyu B. Abdulmalik, 2009 First Published in 2009. Pp 2-17.

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